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Evidence of a potential function for an NLR gene in regulation of imprinting-associated X chromosome genes.

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This was suggested by observation of NLRP7 control of Xist, ZFP36 L1 and ZFP36 L2, KH domain and ILF2/3 genes associated with Xist, and others.